
Self-Representation in John Ashbery's Poem Self Portrait in A Convex Mirror

S.Haripriya Devi Bharadwaj, Research Scholar, (Ph.D.), Acharya Nagarjuna University – 522510, Guntur, A.P.

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Abstract

John Ashbery is a distinguished member of the New York School of Poets. His avant-garde and highly innovative poetry make him one of America's unique poetic voices. *Self-Portrait in a Convex Mirror* is one of John Ashbery's most significant volumes of poetry. The volume's titular poem is considered one of the greatest poems of contemporary American poetry. The poem is a meditation on a self-portrait in a convex mirror by the renaissance painter Parmigianino. The poet speaks through the painter of a distant time and establishes an empathetic relationship with him, transcending spatial and temporal barriers and attempting to explore the interconnectedness between art and the self. The study of the poet's self remains hidden in complex layers of introspective meditations on art and art criticism. The imagery of mirrors is extensively employed throughout the poem. In this poem, Ashbery uses the mode of emphasis or the poetic description of a pictorial or a sculptural piece of art. He also posits that all art is self-reflexive to some extent. This poem narrates a poet's relation to an artwork of the past and how he studies it in the present. This paper aims to analyze the

verse from the thematic perspective of self-representation.

Keywords: avant-garde, meditation, interconnectedness, ekphrasis, and self-representation.

Self Portrait in a Convex Mirror is one of the essential poetry collections of John Ashbery. It was published in the year 1975. The volume title poem is considered one of the greatest poems of American Poetry. Ashbery was awarded almost all significant prizes in American poetry for this celebrated poem. The title for this volume was taken from a painting of the great Italian painter of the late renaissance period Parmigianino. He painted at a time when the style which came to be known as mannerism was at its zenith. Mannerism emerged in the later years of the Italian High Renaissance around 1530 and existed till the end of the century. Mannerism was a style that emphasized exaggeration, form, and contrast of perspective. The poem consists of a descriptive journey that reflects on the relationship between verbal art and painting and between Parmigianino, a mannerist painter of the

sixteenth century, and a modern poet of the twentieth century; resolution and fragmentation are held in equipoise in this poem. And the ekphrastic rendering confers upon the poem continuity, notwithstanding the sudden transitions in the narration. The strophic form confers in the poetry an extraordinary grandeur and continuity in the narration.

The poem begins with the poet describing the minimal background of the portrait and the massive hand in the foreground, which once declares that the picture is that of a reflection in a convex mirror. According to the poet, the face of Parmigianino though fixed, seems to be moving forward and backward like the hand.

As Parmigianino did it, the right hand
 More significant than the head, thrust at
 the viewer
 And swerving quickly away as though to
 protect
 What it advertises, A few leaded panes,
 old beams,
 Fur, pleated muslin, and a coral ring run
 together
 In a movement supporting the face,
 which swims
 Toward and away like the hand
 Except that it is in repose. It is what is
 Sequestered. (1 - 9)

In the following lines, the poet quoted an observation by the famed art critic of renaissance times, Vasari, regarding the genesis of the self-portrait. In the following lines, the poet extends a

parallel between the convexity of the mirror and the soul. The self-portrait of Parmigianino establishes that the soul is circumscribed within the convex mirror, unable to proceed beyond the mirror's gaze. In the following lines, the poet observes that according to Vasari, Pope Clement and his court were astonished by the self-portrait and promised a handsome reward to Parmigianino, which was never given. The poet imagines that the soul of the portrait can't claim autonomy. In the following lines, the poet further imagines that even though the soul is very much alive, it must stay fixed in the painting forever. And there is so much sadness in the picture that one can't gaze at it for long. The portrait reveals that the soul is circumscribed within a limit and can't venture beyond it.

It must move

As little as possible, this is what
 the portrait says.

But there is in that gaze a
 combination

Of tenderness, amusement, and
 regret, so powerful

In its restraint that one can only
 look for a short time. (42 – 46)

In the following lines, the poet observes that the demands of the world and the claims of the self are always held in equipoise. According to the poet, the self is so small in dimension that it can easily fit in a small hollow. In the following lines, the poet elucidates that the word speculum, from which the

phrase speculation came, originally meant mirror in Latin.

Returning to the painting, the poet addresses Parmigianino in a familiar tone and says that his hugely magnified hand is disproportionate. It is vast enough to wreck the symmetry of the painting. And also, the rather ungainly hand could hardly paint such delicate meshes which detain and keep it affixed forever in one place. In the following lines, the poet states that Parmigianino's eyes say that everything exists as a surface fiercely resisting deeper penetration; the self-portrait establishes the premise that appearance is everything. Finally, the surface becomes a reality. And it becomes to analyze the exterior.

But your eyes proclaim

That everything is a surface. The surface is what's there

And nothing can exist except what's there. (80 – 83)

The poet further expresses that no words can accurately retell or provide a commentary on its essence. The self-portrait has the power to assimilate all contradictions within itself. The hand gesture neither denies nor affirms anything but holds everything in suspension.

You will stay on, restive, serene
in Your gesture which is neither
an embrace nor a warning

But which holds something of
both in pure

Affirmation that doesn't affirm
anything. (97 – 100)

In the next strophe, the poet turns his attention away from the portrait for a while. A dull, prosaic reflection of clouds in a puddle leads him to the sharp fragments of his past; as he remembers his friends, the personal reminiscences make him wonder what Parmigianino's thoughts were when he decided to be his model. Probably many people might have come to see him work, and some might have encouraged him; their speech became a part of him, blended into his consciousness, and transmuted his self to such an extent that there wasn't any part of his which could be called his own.

His subjectivity merged with the outer world to such an extent that it ceased to exist and became part of the universe. In the following lines, the poet says that he sees chaos in the round mirror, which paradoxically systematizes everything around the empty eyes.

I see in this only the chaos

Of your round mirror, this
organizes everything

Around the polestar of your eyes
which are empty,

Know nothing, dream but reveal
nothing (122 – 125)

The eyes of the self-portrait reveal
nothing, yet they go on dreaming.
Suddenly the poet feels that he is on a
merry-go ride steadily gathering
momentum. He thinks that all the

personal and non-personal aspects of the self form a neutral band that surrounds him on all sides and finally merges into a magma of interiors. The poet takes for his guide the self-portrait, which remains oblique and direct at the same time; it accepts everything but without affirming anything. In the following lines, the poet remembers a time when the simple events of everyday life held a special significance for him. However, they were as disinterested as a housewife doing the daily chores. In the next lines, the poet expresses that Parmigianino triumphed over the mundane reality by faithfully capturing the present. Here the poet incorporates a quotation. The portrait proclaims the unabashed narcissism of the painter for whom the most significant subject was himself; the poet feels that the selfishness of Parmigianino arrested the vicissitudes of temporal changes and made eternal the fleetingness of youth.

In the circle of your intentions,
specific spars

Remain that perpetuate the
enchantment of self with self

Eyebeams, muslin, coral. It
doesn't matter

Because these are things as they
are today

Before one's shadow ever grew

Out of the field into thoughts of
tomorrow. (147 – 152)

The fourth strophe begins with the poet expressing that the future is easier to comprehend while the present remains

distant and alien. He compares the gift to a landscape that finally gives in to a painter's distrust. In the following lines, the poet incorporates a quotation from the famed art critic Sydney Freedberg.

The poet also says that our dreams seem alien and distant, for they always remain invisible, and we realize this only when they disintegrate and cease to exist like a wave breaking on a rock. The poet expresses that the conception of ideal beauty strangely conforms to the idea of distortion, which is desired intensely. He suggests that the self-portrait with the disproportionately huge hand doesn't seem bizarre but, on the contrary, exhibits an ideal concept of beauty, for the conception of perfect beauty finally converges with distortion.

In the fifth strophe, the poet expresses that as he forgets the self-portrait, it presents the unfamiliar stereotype of the self before him. In the following lines, the poet concurs with the observation made by Freedberg, where he says that the following portraits painted by Parmigianino manifest Mannerist tensions and eccentricities more accurately than the *Self Portrait in a Convex Mirror*. The unity of the high renaissance could be found in the self-portrait but in a distorted manner. And the distortion is apparent to the onlooker; Parmigianino took such astute care to reproduce the distinctive qualities of a convex mirror faithfully that the observer was fooled into believing that he was standing before a convex mirror. The poet makes the incidental observation

that *Self Portrait in a Convex Mirror* is the first mirror portrait; the poet further suggests that the painter beckons the observer to see himself in his self-portrait, which depicts the innermost aspects of his self. And he feels like a character in a Hoffmann opera deprived of a reflection; instead, he thinks that the otherness of the painter is replacing himself. The self-portrait makes the poet confront the self's timeless and time-bound aspects.

In the sixth strophe of the poem, the poet expresses how city life permeates the consciousness of an artist. Parmigianino was influenced by renaissance Rome and its highly charged atmosphere. In the following lines, the poet provides us with details of the painter's life. He also tells us that he saw the painting in Vienna.

Vienna, where the painting is today, where

I saw it with Pierre in the summer of 1959; in New York

Where I am now, which is a logarithm

Of other cities. (255 – 258)

According to him, all cities have urgency, and they are all interconnected to each other with their sense of immediacy. The poet further expresses that the hectic city life can invade the private world of art; he also says that the landscape of his city New York is like an algorithm of other towns, i.e., it has an interconnectedness with other cities. It

has both convergences and divergences with other cities, and the art business is conducted abstruse, for it relies more or less on personal tastes and hearsay. City life sometimes interferes with an artist's work by engendering a sense of insularity. In the following lines, the poet addresses the painter and seeks to know if he can withstand the affectation in the wind.

This wind is compared to laziness that drains away one's vigor once its presence is acknowledged. It's also compared to the whispers of a word that remains incomprehensible but whose presence can be felt. In the following lines, the poet says that this affectation is greatly wanted, like an unlikely challenger who pounds on the doors of an amazed castle. The poet feels that the argument proposed by the painter has long become redundant, as any answers needed to be emerging. And though the statement expounded by Parmigianino may have become obsolete, another life lies hidden in the depths of the self-portrait. The argument expostulated by Parmigianino doesn't remain static but goes on to change, corresponding to the changes in time. The view, while reversing, stimulates gradual changes in the onlooker. Finally, the self-portrait becomes a metaphor for life. According to the poet, the self-portrait undercuts any definitive ekphrastic interpretation, yet it beckons change by constantly defying mimesis. The poet suggests that art and life are subjective and that this inter-

subjectivity links him with the painter of a faraway time.

The seventh strophe begins with the poet saying that a light breeze, like when a page is turned, makes him face himself. He surmises there isn't an easy escape from the self and the immediate reality surrounding him. Suddenly he experiences constriction after the encounter, and facing the self seems a demanding task. In this context, he quotes the art critic Berg and from Shakespeare's drama *Cymbeline*, the words Imogen spoke. In the following lines, the poet states that anything beautiful appears only when seen about a specific life, real or imagined.

But it is inevitable that

What is beautiful seems so only
with a specific

Life experienced or not,
channeled into some form

Steeped in the nostalgia of a
collective past. (327 – 330)

He feels that many like him might have experienced the same enthusiasm and a sense of meaning many years ago after seeing the self-portrait of Parmigianino. In the following lines, he says he keeps consulting the reflection that has long ceased to be his own, for it has turned vacant.

I go on consulting

This mirror that is no longer mine

For as much brisk vacancy as is to
be

My portion this time. (337 – 340)

In the following lines, he says that the self is like a vase that accommodates everything. The self-portrait is an example of the accommodative self and an entity that transcends the time-ridden world. It can't be taken as an ineffectual action but as an embodiment of a pure whole that can absorb within itself all complexities.

In the following lines, the poet expresses that once love was an essential aspect of his life and had an overweening presence, but now its presence could only be felt and seen. He further exposts that love leads one to further meanderings.

In the following lines, the poet expresses that there was a time when he used to think that the present seemed the same to everyone, but this uncertainty was resolved when one faced one's gift. In the following lines, he refers to the straw-colored space of the corridor leading to the painting which is dark in comparison giving the impression that it is imaginary and not actual. He further queries if this poetic sunlight has its abode in the ever-changing present from which one unsuccessfully tries to escape, only to fall back into it, which flows continuously like a waterwheel. In the following lines, he returns to the museum and says he would like to get out of it as the closing time is approaching, and everyone seems to be pushing them in. He also says that one can only live in the museum for a while. The extremely

difficult renaissance techniques of painting that took a lifetime to master are seldom given the admiration that they deserve, and they are reduced to the black illustrations in a coffee table book.

In the following lines time, the poet expresses that time can never be transcended. In the museum, none alludes to the passing of time, for doing so might mean drawing attention to their selves. And paradoxically, by arresting the passing of time, the self-portrait makes apparent to the spectators what they have been trying in vain to evade. According to the poet, the result is never in agreement with the artist's original intention, and then there might have been distractions further diverting him from his goal. The poet uses the metaphor of the game called Chinese Whispers to illustrate his point.

This always
It happens, as in the game
Where a whispered phrase passed
around the room
Ends up as something completely
different.
It is the principle that makes
works of art unlike
What the artist intended. Often he
finds
He has omitted the thing he
started to say
In the first place. (449 – 457)

The poet observes that an artist is always pleased with the result despite the shortcomings and the self-blame,

believing that he can bring into being his imaginary vision. The poet also posits that although the history of creation progresses according to strict laws, we can't say the same of the results of the imagination, which we wanted so despairingly to come into being. The poet also expresses that Parmigianino might have experienced the same predicament while working on his life-threatening project. And probably Parmigianino couldn't realize or paint the essence of himself, for his interiority always eluded him. Finally, he settled for the smooth outward finish of the painting.

In the following lines, the poet surmises that anything beyond this otherness touches every aspect of life, slightly or profoundly. This otherness forcibly places all artistic creations on a monstrous peak, ambivalently poised, at once too near to be ignored and too far to be interposed with. He compares the otherness to a ship of an unknown country suddenly entering a harbor; with the entering of the boat, all extraneous matters disrupt one's day, and the fertile thought associations that till now came so frequently stop coming altogether. This otherness is located in the world of experience. There may be many inter-subjective reasons preventing an artist from expressing what he intended to say. In the following lines, the poet states that the knowledge of others is of little help. And there can't be a singular definition regarding the universe, and subsequently, the subjective analyses of others are of little use. In these lines, he advocates

solipsism. He also proposes a critique of pluralistic thought.

Each person

Has one big theory to explain the universe

But it doesn't tell the whole story

And in the end, it is what is outside him

That matters to him and especially to us

Who have been given no help whatever

In decoding our man-size quotient and must rely upon

On second-hand knowledge. (508 – 515)

There was a time when certain aspects distanced him from the humdrum of daily life. He wishes for such a paradise, but then he realizes that such a paradise can never be attained. For art has long ceased to be the 'exotic refuge'. The poet suggests that art has lost its capacity to be a haven, he doubts if the mimetic quality of art can be a liberating experience from the rigors of external reality. According to the poet, high art and its various manifestations attain the form of a fixed 'frozen gesture' etched on the background of a greater reality. He further feels that the artistic representations are of little use except for igniting the imagination. He thinks of them as a hindrance in a world that necessitates the mimicry of many roles.

In the following lines, the poet addresses Parmigianino and requests him

to withdraw the hand, which functions both as a shield and a greeting and conveys to the viewer the convexity of art.

Therefore I pray you to withdraw that hand,

Offer it no longer as a shield or greeting,

The security of a greeting, Francesco:

There is room for one bullet in the chamber

Our looking through the wrong end

Of the telescope as you fall back at a speed

From faster than of light to flatten ultimately

Among the features of the room is an invitation

Never mailed, the "it was all a dream."

Syndrome, though the "all" tells tersely

Enough how it wasn't. It's Existence

It was natural, though troubled, and the ache

This waking dream can never drown out

The diagram still sketched on the wind,

Chosen meant for me and materialized

In the disguising radiance of my room. (537 – 552)

He also suggests that art is suicidal. The painting thus becomes, for the poet, the wrong end of a telescope

that momentarily enabled the possibility of transcendence. He compares his experience to that of an invitation that never gets mailed. At the same time, he acknowledges that the 'waking dream' can't be termed simply as an illusion; he also poignantly observes that the sadness and the resultant desultoriness can never erase the painting that remains sketched on the wind. The phrase 'waking dream' was probably taken from John Keats's famous poem *Ode to a Nightingale*.

In the concluding lines of this poem, the poet observes that city life is alienating; although he gets absorbed in its goings-on, he remains an outsider. He compares city life to the mirrored eye of an insect. All the events happen on its balcony and continue therein while the action is like the 'cold syrupy flow of a pageant.' He feels distanced from the painting as he searches through the April sunlight for reasons behind his alienation. He feels deprived of the wholeness that was part of his experience's momentary transcendence.

The hand holds no chalk.
And each part of the whole falls
off
And cannot know it knew, except
Here and there, in cold pockets
Of remembrance, whispers out of
time. (561 – 565)

Many critics regard this poem as an epiphany of "the enchantment of self with self". The poet proposes through the self-portrait of Parmigianino his self-portrait and that art is both timeless and

time-bound. The meditation on the painting is never continuous but interlaced with critical insights and quotations from art critics. In each strophe, there is an alternation of the passive and the active voice; we also find a remarkable blending of descriptive force and reflective placidity. There is also certain diffusiveness in the poem. The self-portrait proposes that everything exists as a surface that can never be transcended. This poem can also be taken as an internal debate on the inter-subjectivity between art and life and between continuity and discontinuity in art. The poet puts forward the proposition that despite being mimetic, art constantly defies mimesis by being timeless, while the inter-subjectivity between art and life remains ambivalent. All the same, it remains an unfulfilled reflection of reality as well as an imperfect representation of life. The poet also posits that all art is self-reflexive and obliquely autobiographical and that the personality of the artist can never be divorced from his creations. The poem is simultaneously self-referential and non-referential.

The poet also infers that although it's easy to construct the self, its exterior aspects can never be unraveled. In the final strophe, the poet surmises that the self can never be analyzed objectively, being located in the world of experience and subject to the vicissitudes of temporal change. And transcendence remains an unrealized possibility, a momentary perception that can never be apprehended in its totality. And as David Shapiro has

observed with great insight in his book, *John Ashbery: An Introduction to Poetry*. (1980)

Ashbery wants the poem to be a trace of the mind tracing the poem. The poem remains an object, but an object was constantly demanding subjectivity in the most Kierkegaardian sense. The poem uses the subjective method because that is all we have. Criticism has deleted too much of this personal element. (11)

The poet finds convergences and equivalences between manneristic art, emphasizing highly stylized distortion, and his poetry, whose most defining characteristic is its extreme experimentation. The self-portrait's most defining feature is the vast hand that almost threatens to disrupt the symmetry but also, at the same time, enforces a peculiar order by superimposing on the viewer the distinctive characteristics of mannerism. Mannerism's most outstanding characteristic was its emphasis on distortion and chaos and an excessive fondness for mirrors and framing devices. Ashbery sees in mannerism the genesis of modernist art; he also establishes in this poem the interconnectedness between visual art and verbal art.

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